

Role and Significance of English Language Teaching & Learning Through Apps

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Abstract:

In our contemporary society, technology pervades every aspect of our lives. The pedagogical approach to teaching has been altered due to the extensive prevalence of technology. The terms "E-Learning" and "Technology in Education" have become widely used in all educational environments. Integrating technology into education is essential since it fulfils the requirements of contemporary students. The contemporary educational environment significantly diverges from the conventional classroom. Conventional methods, primarily based on lectures and repetitive learning, limit the acquisition of the English language to mere memory and do not effectively develop it as a talent for learners. The field of education has experienced a significant increase in technical innovation in recent decades, and the significance of this cannot be exaggerated. The utilization of the Internet, Twitter, Blogs, YouTube, Skype, mobile phones, interactive boards, and other emerging technologies has not only heightened the level of stimulus but also enhanced student participation and fostered genuine interactivity inside the classroom. The use of e-learning in the acquisition of English as a second language, specifically, has experienced significant expansion over an extended period. The present paper focuses on the role and importance of e-learning in the field of English language teaching.

Keywords: Role of technology in education, E-learning tools, English language teaching, learning through apps etc.

Introduction

The advancement and widespread adoption of information technology has led to an increasing amount of literature emphasizing the necessity of E-learning to enhance the convenience and ease of studying English as a second language (ESL), depending on the country or setting. Currently, e-learning mostly involves utilizing the internet as a tool for teaching and learning, either as a primary or secondary educational resource. The utilization of E-learning tools as Information and Communication Technology (ICT), encompassing communication devices and software products such as overhead projectors, projectors, interactive boards, blogs, the world wide Web, cameras, audio equipment, scanners, computers,

printers, I-pads, e-mails, video conferencing, and various others, not only impacts and sustains educational content within schools but also influences and facilitates learning beyond the school environment.

Extensive studies have been conducted on the potential advantages of utilizing technology in this manner for both educators and learners. E-learning eliminates the temporal and spatial constraints that are present in traditional learning environments.

Teachers can effectively enhance students' English language proficiency by utilizing creative English Language Teaching (ELT) strategies such as English songs, movie clips, drama, ads, sports comments, and other methods. In addition, E-learning programs provide English learners with access to excellent materials and the opportunity to directly engage with native English speakers. Students have the option to enhance their English skills in listening, vocal communication, reading, and writing using various E-learning programs.

Teaching English in the Past

The instruction of languages in general and English Language Teaching (ELT) specifically, has undergone significant transformation throughout the centuries. When English was made a mandatory subject in the student's curriculum, it posed a problem for English language teachers. However, they approached it as a 'Knowledge' subject rather than a 'Skill' subject, with their primary objective being to prepare students to pass examinations alone. Consequently, they implemented the 'Grammar-Translation Method,' wherein the instructor elucidated each concept to the students in their native language to facilitate comprehension and acquisition of the English language.

Despite neglecting the learners' speaking skills, this method continues to be widely favoured by most teachers in its altered version. In addition, various other methods were employed, including the bilingual technique, direct method, audio-lingual method, structural approach, situational education, and communicative language teaching. However, none of these methods were considered to be perfect. Since then, ELT has oscillated between different approaches as language teachers continuously seek new and more efficient methods.

Teaching English in the Present

The people of the twenty-first century encounter novel choices, prospects, and challenges as a result of the widespread integration of technology into every facet of life. In

the present era, educational institutions must go beyond the traditional model of transmitting a fixed set of information from teacher to student within a specific timeframe. Instead, they should prioritize the development of "learning to learn" abilities, which involve acquiring knowledge and skills that facilitate lifelong learning. The present requirement is to provide individuals with a high level of competency in the English language, which can only be achieved through a suitable combination of educational and online learning resources (advanced technologies).

The incorporation of e-learning tools into educational processes has disrupted conventional teaching and learning paradigms. E-learning encompasses a range of technological tools and systems that competent and creative educators may utilize to enhance the quality of teaching and learning environments. These tools are employed to enhance students' learning by making it more captivating, inspiring, stimulating, and significant. These instruments have been recognized as potentially powerful facilitators of educational transformation and advancement.

Effectiveness of Technology based learning in English Language Teaching

Technology based learning is an effective tool for creating productive learning environments that inspire students and guarantee valuable and significant learning results. E-learning offers a substantial chance for students to engage in reflection and concentration. In an e-learning environment, computers can efficiently rectify writing errors, enabling students to enhance their skills by learning from their mistakes. The software can detect mistakes in writing and offer suggestions on how to rectify them, potentially enhancing student learning.

Promoting key learning skills through E-learning

Implementing e-learning software for students can facilitate the enhancement of their auditory comprehension abilities. Proficiency in English speaking is a highly valuable skill, and e-learning can be beneficial in improving speaking abilities through the use of English-language chat rooms. Given the limited usage of English in our country, the implementation of e-learning will facilitate the enhancement of students' oral communication skills. Chat rooms offer students a valuable opportunity to enhance their speaking abilities, offering unique options that are not found in traditional educational environments.

Promoting Independent Learning through E-learning

E-learning accommodates various learning styles since it aligns with an individual's innate, customary, and favoured method of acquiring, assimilating, and remembering novel information and skills. When students are allowed to learn in their preferred manner without any external pressure or influence, they often employ strategies that directly reflect their preferred learning style. E-learning provides students with abundant resources, enabling them to learn regardless of their circumstances. Students can gain relevant information without being physically present in the classroom, and they do not always require the presence of a teacher. However, utilizing e-learning without prior experience and supervision would pose a challenge. This underscores the importance of the teacher's involvement in facilitating students' utilization of e-learning resources. E-learning offers immediate feedback, which is quite beneficial. Students also find e-learning tools inspiring as they can learn autonomously without teacher supervision or intervention.

Promoting Flexible Learning through App-learning

Students utilizing app-learning have round-the-clock access to their coursework, enabling them to allocate additional time to compensate for any missed class material. Rather than just prioritizing the accessibility of online resources, it is more important to emphasize the flexibility provided by the possibility to practice at any given time. Students can get schoolwork from school, home, or any other location as long as they have access to a computer and an internet connection. Teachers can possess an equivalent degree of adaptability in terms of overseeing their students' advancement. E-learning eliminates geographical and spatial limitations for students. This highlights the fact that students from different geographic regions can easily communicate by using e-learning materials. This feature can encourage students to engage with others, regardless of their location, and motivate them to utilize the characteristics of e-interactive learning. The Internet has a global scope and can offer access to a vast amount of international information. In a similar vein, e-learning provides English students with the opportunity to engage with native English speakers and have access to crucial language-learning materials. Learning through various apps enables students to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the English language, encompassing the skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Promoting Interactive Learning through E-learning

E-learning is a dynamic technology that enhances communication between students and professors. E-learning is a collection of advanced technological tools that enable teachers and students to connect online, outside of the traditional classroom setting, to enhance the process of teaching and learning English. Utilizing e-learning for English learning and teaching can facilitate the establishment of an engaging and dynamic relationship between students and teachers. E-learning facilitates global communication among students using chat rooms, offering a more convenient, flexible, and interactive experience.

Advantages of Learning through Apps

- It enhances and extends the duration of involvement between students and educational materials, students and instructors, and students.
- Even with the absence of physical presence in the classroom, students can still engage in studying.
- Allows students and teachers to exchange information or feedback about educational content, hence optimizing the limited in-person interaction time for subject-related discussions.
- Enhance the calibre and efficacy of teachers by implementing superior instructional models and resources that are easily comprehensible and accessible to students.

E-learning tools in English language Teaching

Numerous e-learning applications are available for English language instruction. Below are some of the stated e-learning tools:

Use of the Internet for English Language Teaching

The internet serves as a repository of both authentic English content and a wealth of information in the form of articles, courses, conferences, and more. The teacher can utilize e-mail as a means of disseminating homework assignments to students, as well as administering online assessments. Parents can remotely view their children's work at any given time using the internet. Students now have the option to attend lessons remotely with a webcam and access class materials such as worksheets and notes from electronic online whiteboards. Schools are

interconnected through a network and engage in online collaboration for projects and sharing of materials.

Each educational institution possesses its digital presence. There is currently a wide range of free software tools accessible on the Internet that students can utilize. Spelling Bee is an online software designed to aid children in accurately spelling English words. The teacher can choose the desired level of difficulty at which they wish to teach their students.

Use of E-Dictionaries for English Language Teaching

When acquiring a new language, students depend on dictionaries as dependable references since they enable them to have assurance in their conjectures regarding the significance of unfamiliar phrases. Therefore, dictionaries can serve as a beneficial resource during the language acquisition process, provided that learners utilize them in a regulated manner and avoid becoming excessively dependent on them.

Use of YouTube for English Language Teaching

YouTube videos can be employed in an English Language Teaching (ELT) classroom to enhance vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, voice modulation, and various other aspects of the English language. The primary advantage of employing YouTube as a tool for teaching English is its ability to offer genuine illustrations of persons employing the English language in ordinary circumstances. The teacher might utilize it to facilitate students in enhancing their listening, speaking, reading, and writing proficiency. The teacher has the option to choose a movie segment that is suitable for the children's proficiency level and present it to them as short film excerpts. Furthermore, the teacher can generate worksheets in advance that are tailored to the movie excerpts, and then distribute them to the students to be completed during the movie viewing. Enabling the option to access news headlines on YouTube helps enhance one's listening skills. Due to the rapid summarization of the news, the teacher may instruct students to listen to the headlines and arrange them in a specific sequence. Consequently, engaging in this activity could be quite beneficial for children since it can greatly improve their abilities in listening and writing.

Use of Skype for English Language Teaching

Skype enables teachers and students to engage in collaborative work regardless of their geographical location. It provides students in a foreign language class with multiple opportunities to connect with classes in other countries and enhance their language skills. Teachers can offer guidance or aid with assignments to students through the use of Skype. Students have the opportunity to engage in activities such as reading, presenting, performing, collaborating on writing projects and conducting research projects with their peers. Additionally, they have the opportunity to participate in professional development activities within and beyond the school district.

Use of Twitter for English Language Teaching

Twitter has an unlimited capacity to involve students in studying subjects as an online educational technology tool. The teacher has the freedom to select any genre for the story and can begin the activity by tweeting a story opening to the students and inviting their feedback. The teacher can assess the contributions of all members of the Twitter network once they have all engaged in the building of the storyline. Editing, story structuring, original writing, and good language usage are integral components of this process. The teacher can instruct students to select a word of the week and share it on the network via Twitter, requesting synonyms, homonyms, and antonyms. After receiving all of the replies, the teacher can thoroughly verify their accuracy and establish a connection between the difficult terms to assist students in enhancing their vocabulary.

Use of Smartboard for English Language Teaching

Smart boards can be utilized by teachers to instruct language arts in a student-centred fashion. Language teachers can utilize Smart Boards to enhance reading and comprehension skills, as well as instruct students in grammar and writing. Teachers can utilize a Smart Board to facilitate interactive instruction for students by integrating video, music, web browsing, and word processing. Word games are an excellent means of bringing students together and reviewing vocabulary. Learners have the option to utilize anagrams or jumbled sentences, or they can request synonyms, antonyms, lexis, or collocation terms.

Use of Mobile Phones for English Language Teaching

Mobile phones have a wide range of applications as educational tools. The teacher can instruct the students to produce a picture documentary by utilizing the camera feature on their smartphones. The teacher can assign a documentary theme to the students. After capturing an adequate amount of images, students have the option to post their documentaries to websites such as Flickr. They can then include narrative summaries for each picture, allowing them to share their work with teachers, classmates, family, and friends. Rather than consulting a dictionary, students can simply utilize their translator, and instead of searching through books to locate a piece of literature, they can access it online and be directed to it.

Use of Podcasting for English Language Teaching

A podcast is a compilation of digital media files that are broadcast over the Internet through syndication feeds, allowing them to be played back on mobile devices and desktops. Using podcasts in the classroom is straightforward. To utilize in the classroom, the instructor has the option to acquire a diverse range of complimentary ESL podcasts on the Internet. The teacher may also provide a music podcast that familiarizes students with the culture and the creative use of words, or news channels that educate students on intonation and emphasis.

Use of Blog for English Language Teaching

Blogging has gained significant appeal, especially in the realm of education, due to its exceptional ability to disseminate knowledge and stimulate discussions. A significant number of educators opt to utilize these innovative methods to facilitate the instruction of students and gain familiarity with diverse types of social media, as opposed to relying solely on textbooks and conventional approaches. Teachers should encourage students to regularly visit the blog. It is imperative that they promptly address student posts by composing a concise reply regarding the topic. Additionally, it is advisable to inquire about the learner's writing to encourage and promote writing skills. Posting to the blog may be mandatory and will be evaluated as a component of the course. Students should be encouraged to submit their writing homework on the blog, rather than turning it in to the teacher.

Teacher's Role in English Language Teaching

It is crucial to acknowledge that teachers may have a deficiency in the requisite comprehension to integrate the two pedagogical approaches (conventional and E-learning).

Hence, educators must possess knowledge of how to incorporate technology into the academic syllabus. Considerations:

- Teachers should be encouraged to develop proficiency in e-learning by acquiring the ability to find educational materials, choose and utilize effective teaching methods, track their progress, and successfully apply their skills and knowledge to achieve learning goals.
- Teachers should instruct their students on strategies for understanding and extracting knowledge from genuine resources. By doing this, students will enhance their ability to acquire the skills and techniques necessary to comprehend genuine stuff.

E-learning Pedagogical Strategies for building English Language skills

Pedagogical strategies should encompass teaching programs that are efficacious and grounded in the specific teaching tasks and characteristics of the students. Additionally, these strategies should involve the careful selection of suitable teaching content, methods, and approaches. When e-learning is employed for teaching English, the pedagogical strategies undergo significant changes. E-learning can expedite students' acquisition of English by employing pedagogical strategies that foster linguistic sensitivity and enhance listening comprehension and expressive proficiency. Language growth does not rely on erroneous activities or grammar, but rather on the student's continuous and personal practice. The e-learning pedagogical methodologies for enhancing various English skills are outlined below:

Developing Listening Skill

The process of acquiring language skills should commence by focusing on the auditory sense. E-learning empowers students to choose their educational resources. Electronic learning can include audio lessons to enhance students' listening skills, which may involve the utilization of videos for both auditory and visual learning. For kids in grades 6-9, the teacher can help them find resources that are both suitable in terms of complexity and aligned with their initial interests. They typically acquire knowledge quickly and, without the guidance of an instructor, will promptly recognize highly pertinent educational resources. Likewise, professors may suggest some materials for group discussion, while students in grades 10 to 12

can also independently discover additional resources. E-learning is a more valuable resource than textbooks for enhancing language ability.

Reading Skill

E-learning enables students to engage with subjects that pique their interest. There is an abundance of reading material available on the internet that can assist kids in enhancing their reading abilities.

Speaking Skill

The teacher may prompt students to elaborate on an occurrence, encompassing details like the individuals involved, the time, location, actions, and motivations, drawing from the learning materials they have engaged with through listening, reading, and translation exercises. This exercise aims to enhance students' proficiency in oral communication.

Writing Skill

Upon engaging in the activities of listening, reading, and speaking, students can be prompted to transcribe the information to depict the event itself, as well as their sentiments, observations, and so on. By engaging in this process, students can enhance their proficiency in expressing information in the English language.

Conclusion

We currently reside in an epoch characterized by an overwhelming abundance of information. In the past, information was scarce, but now we are overwhelmed by an abundance of knowledge. E-learning tools are revolutionizing both our world and our approach to learning. E-learning utilizes computers and the Internet to revolutionize educational methods, hence improving the effectiveness of teaching and learning. Language proficiency is a cognitive talent that requires the application of suitable educational techniques and training methods. The global prominence and importance of the English language have significantly increased in recent decades, as it has become a universally spoken language. Technology constantly advances to satisfy the ever-changing demands of the present moment. We currently reside in the twenty-first century, which is characterized by significant technical advancements. Previously, learners were not provided with any activities that fostered productivity, creativity, or constructive involvement to enhance their proficiency in the four language skills.

Nevertheless, if language instructors persist in employing traditional teaching methods, the necessary objectives of English language acquisition may not be achieved in the present global context. Individuals possessing foresight and a logical approach, conversely, will acknowledge the significance of e-learning in the realm of English instruction. E-learning will not only alleviate teachers from their burdensome duties, but it will also facilitate the acquisition of English for students.

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